

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

THE BODY AS A BATTLEFIELD: THE POLITICS OF SEXUAL CONTROL IN PROCESSES OF DE-COLONIZATION AND THE ESTABLISHMENT OF NATIONAL IDENTITY

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Abstract

The aim of the article is to examine how the policy of sexual control is implemented by the authorities. Sexuality is viewed not only as a biological need, but also as an instrument of power, regulation of society, and social inequality. The principle of bodily autonomy is analyzed as the right of every person to independently, without outside interference, coercion or violence, dispose of their own body. The key philosophical and anthropological concepts that address this problem are traced. The symbolism of some sexual perversions is also analyzed.

Keywords: philosophical anthropology, political anthropology, corporeality, bodily autonomy, symbol, symbolization, power, political pressure, perversion.

Introduction

"The body as a battlefield" is a concept that reveals how privacy and reproductive rights become the object of political pressure. In the context of decolonization, control over the body and gender roles is used by imperial centers to suppress culture, while national liberation movements often try to mobilize the body to assert their own identity.

The politics of sexual control have been studied by scholars in philosophy, history, sociology, and gender studies. They view sexuality not only as a biological need, but also as a tool of power, regulation of society, and social inequality. Key scholars who have studied this aspect include M. Foucault, J. Weeks, G. Rubin, J. Butler, and K. McKinnon.

Michel Foucault is a French philosopher and historian, author of the seminal work *The History of Sexuality* (*La volonté de savoir*); he argued that in modern societies, power controls people not only through violence, but also through discourses about sexuality, imposing certain norms, classifications (e.g., "normal" and "deviant"), and standards of behavior [3, p. 76]. Jeffrey Weeks is a British sociologist and researcher, one of the most prominent historians of sexuality. He analyzed how sexuality becomes a field of political struggle, and the state, religion, and institutions attempt to exercise control over the body, rights, and identity through the prism of "sexual politics". Gayle Rubin is an American anthropologist and gender theorist. She is known for her work *Thinking About Sex: A Radical Theory of the Politics of Sexuality*, in which she analyzed the social hierarchy that legitimizes some sexual practices (e.g., heterosexual and reproductive) and criminalizes or stigmatizes others. Judith Butler is a philosopher and queer theorist. In her writings (including *The Gender Trouble*), she has examined how heteronormative societies and institutions coerce gender roles and sexual desires through established norms. Catharine MacKinnon is a lawyer and feminist theorist.

She has explored the relationship between sexuality, gender inequality, and law, arguing that in patriarchal societies, sexual control over women is often institutionalized in the form of sexual violence, harassment, and pornography.

However, this problematic field has not been fully explored. In particular, some key anthropological symbols that allow us to reveal the problematic of sexuality in the political sphere have not yet been studied.

Main part.

Bodily autonomy is the right of every person to independently, without external interference, coercion or violence, dispose of their own body. It is a fundamental principle of human rights, based on the sovereignty of the individual, free will and self-determination. This concept encompasses several key aspects: a) personal choice, the right to make decisions about their own health and medical intervention (for example, consent to surgery or reproductive rights); b) inviolability, i.e. protection from physical violence, sexual exploitation and coercion; c) bodily integrity, i.e. the inviolability of the physical body, when no one has the right to harm or use it without your will [2].

Empires and authoritarian regimes impose their own demographic, sexual and gender policies in order to break local social structures [1]. Control is exercised through: a) reproductive regulation This is forced sterilization, prohibition or imposition of abortions in order to change the demographic composition of the population; b) imposition of patriarchy (the destruction of local egalitarian traditions and the consolidation of rigid gender roles, where women are viewed exclusively as a resource for the reproduction of the nation, and men as an instrument of military expansion); c) criminalization of sexuality, which finds its expression through the persecution of identities that deviate from imperial "traditional" or religious standards. Liberation from colonial influence requires not only the achievement of po-

litical independence, but also the decolonization of consciousness and body, the rejection of imposed colonial standards of corporeality, beauty and sexuality [4, p. 53].

In the struggle for survival and national identity (particularly during armed conflicts), citizens' bodies are deeply militarized. Sexual violence during war is used as a weapon of genocide, aimed at destroying national identity by destroying the physical and psychological integrity of victims. Physical loss and disability become part of collective trauma and national pride. The affirmation of national identity is often contradictory. On the one hand, society strives for European standards of freedom, on the other hand, there is a strong demand for a return to "traditional family values" as a protection against assimilation.

The most egregious documented historical and contemporary case of colonial policies regarding bodily autonomy is the forced and coerced sterilization of indigenous peoples (Indians and Inuit) in North America. This practice has been ongoing since the first half of the 20th century and is still being documented in some places in the 21st century. This is how this policy of control over reproductive rights played out in practice. Canada and the United States had laws on sexual sterilization (for example, in the province of Alberta, the Sexual Sterilization Act, which was in force from 1928 to 1972). These policies were based on racist and eugenic ideas, according to which indigenous peoples were considered "inferior" or prone to "deviance". Although indigenous peoples constituted a tiny percentage of the population, they constituted a disproportionately large share of those forcibly sterilized—about 25%.

Many indigenous women were forced to sign consent forms for tubal ligation or were forced to do so (under threat of not having their babies returned) at their most vulnerable, during intense pain or after a caesarean section. The procedures were often disguised as other surgical procedures or performed without proper consent, a direct violation of the fundamental human right to control one's own body. In the United States alone, up to 42% of indigenous women of childbearing age were sterilized in the 1970s, often without their knowledge or under duress.

Even after the repeal of official eugenics laws, the practice of spontaneous or forced sterilization in medical institutions continued in Canada until 2018. This policy is considered by human rights activists, in particular the NWAC (Native Women's Association of Canada), as a form of systemic colonial violence and a component of ethnic cleansing and genocide, as it is aimed at controlling the reproduction of an entire people [7].

Sexual perversions: a symbolic dimension. Viewing political violence through the lens of sexual perversion is a powerful metaphor used in psychoanalysis, philosophical anthropology, and social philosophy. Both phenomena (political violence and perversions) are based on similar mechanisms: the violation of boundaries, the dominance of one person (or system) over another, and the acquisition of power instead of partnership. As in sexual perversions (where the sexual act becomes a means of control rather than intimacy), political violence uses coercion to demonstrate power.

The repressive state apparatus or dictator imposes its will on society in the same way that the perpetrator imposes a script on the victim, ignoring her sovereignty and needs.

Lacanian psychoanalysis reinterprets the interaction of power and desire through several key concepts. Let us consider them briefly.

1. Desire as "the desire of the Other." Lacan argued that human desire is never directed at the object of utilitarian need. It is always the desire for what the "Other" desires (society, the system of power, authority). We desire power or what power imposes on us because we seek recognition and fill the ontological void in our own identity.

2. The power of law and the temptation to violate. Lacan repeatedly emphasized the inseparable connection between power/law (the Law of the Father, the Symbolic Order) and desire. The very act of prohibition (for example, taboos or restrictions imposed by authority) paradoxically eroticizes the object. Desire always tries to violate the law, but it needs this law to exist and continue its endless search [6, p. 212].

3. Hidden pleasure in the mechanisms of power. Developing Lacan's ideas, S. Žižek notes that submission to power does not arise exclusively from coercion or ideological blindness. The subject finds perverse pleasure (*jouissance*) in performing the rituals that power demands. This eroticization of the structures of dependence makes submission psychologically attractive. Pleasure is hidden not as a result of the application of power, but in the very process of the functioning of power [8, p. 116].

In his Seminar XVII, Lacan identified four basic discourses that describe forms of human communication and power: the Master's discourse, where direct power and knowledge are articulated; the university discourse, the hysterical discourse; and the analyst's discourse. Power is understood here as a structure based on knowledge and unconscious desires. The mechanisms of power attempt to provide stability to the subject, but desire (as a primary process) remains something that these structures cannot fully control.

Just as sexual perversion diverts the sexual act from its natural purpose (procreation and mutual love), political violence distorts the very essence of politics. Instead of being a space for social contract and development, politics is transformed into an instrument of humiliation, traumatization and destruction of the other, which is a direct violation of fundamental human rights. The fundamental feature of sexual violence is the transformation of a living person into an object (a thing, a means of pleasure). Political violence (e.g. war, repression, genocide) works in the same way: it devalues human life, turning masses of people into "cannon fodder", statistics or tools for achieving geopolitical goals.

Let's consider some common sexual perversions in a symbolic way.

Sexual sadism. It becomes a political symbol when power, domination and violence are used as an instrument of domination, and the infliction of suffering is transformed into an end in itself or a means of control. This phenomenon is considered through the prism of politics, sociology and psychoanalysis in some aspects:

a). Extreme domination and humiliation. In politics, sadism symbolizes the transformation of human dignity into a resource for demonstrating absolute power. When political regimes (for example, totalitarian or authoritarian) destroy legal and ethical boundaries, they use sadistic practices - torture, public humiliation, repression.

This becomes a symbol of the fact that the state controls not only the bodies, but also the will of people; b) Deviance as the norm. W. Reich linked political sadism with the suppression of natural sexuality and personal freedom by the patriarchal state. According to this theory, sexual repression and authoritarianism go hand in hand, generating mass aggression; c) The Dark Tetrad. Modern social research studies the connection between radical political views and personality traits, including "everyday sadism" and psychopathy (getting pleasure from harming others). In political discourse, sadism can be used as a means of propaganda, when political leaders or movements sacralize cruelty in order to mobilize supporters against "enemies". In extreme manifestations, for example, in neo-Nazi or misanthropic groups, sadistic elements become part of identity, emblems, or symbolism.

Sexual sadomasochism as a political symbol is used to metaphorically describe unequal power relations, where dominance and submission become instruments of social contract, propaganda or protest. Sadomasochistic practices are often mentioned to describe the pathological dependence between society and authoritarian leaders. The concept of "political sadomasochism" describes a situation where the authorities use repression (sadism), and part of society demonstrates approval, voluntary submission or even dependence (masochism) for the sake of an imaginary order or security. The most famous example of the symbolization of this perversion in art is the performance "Seven Meditations on Political Sado-Masochism", created in 1973 by the legendary experimental collective The Living Theatre.

The play is set after members of the troupe were imprisoned and brutally treated by the military dictatorship in Brazil. Authors Julian Beck and Judith Malina used sadomasochism as an allegory to visualize the coercion of the state over the individual (war, money, property, death), calling for an anarchic revolution. E. Fromm's concept of "escape from freedom" describes masochistic tendencies as the desire of the individual to get rid of the burden of responsibility and dissolve in the power of the leader or state. In this context, sadomasochism serves as a tool for analyzing the nature of dictatorships and fascism. In modern queer politics and feminism, the attitude to sadomasochism as a symbol is different. Some theorists view conscious sadomasochistic practices as a subversion of patriarchal norms. Through the concept of consensus, security, and voluntariness, they symbolize the deconstruction of power hierarchies, showing that any power can be rethought and controlled [5, p. 30].

Exhibitionism as a metaphor describes the demonstrative public behavior of politicians; it symbolizes the rejection of privacy for the sake of political dividends, self-admiration of power, playing the public and ma-

nipulation. In the modern context, this symbol manifests itself through several key aspects: demonstrative openness (hypertransparency) as a demonstration of details of personal life or "candid" work on camera to create an image of "one's" politician. This often hides real political intentions and manipulates the emotions of voters; "politics as a performance", when instead of deep legislative work, the emphasis is on bright, but meaningfully empty performances. The goal of such behavior is to instantly attract attention (hype), and not to solve social problems. Just as psychological exhibitionism violates boundaries, political exhibitionism imposes information noise on society, forcing citizens to become passive spectators, regardless of their desire. This symbol emphasizes the transition from traditional political responsibility to an era of spectacle, where form dominates substance and shocking replaces a program of action.

Voyeurism. In a political context, it turns into a metaphor for a socio-political phenomenon where the public plays the role of a passive spectator, watching the emotional dramas, betrayals and "dirty laundry" of the authorities as an exciting reality show, consciously refusing to participate in the real governance of the state. Political voyeurism is based on several key aspects: politics as a reality show (tabloidization), when instead of discussing program decisions, the focus shifts to scandals, compromising information and the personal lives of politicians. Citizens consume it as entertainment; the illusion of control (panopticon), when voters have the idea that they see everything and control the authorities thanks to social networks or the media, although in reality this process is often skillfully directed by the politicians themselves. The transformation of citizens into spectators weakens democratic institutions. Instead of being active subjects (voters), people become spectators who discuss political theater, but do not influence it. Live broadcasts of meetings, drone videos, public showdowns create an atmosphere of openness, which is often only a simulation of transparency. This phenomenon is exploited to distract society from real systemic problems and transfer political struggle to the plane of emotional spectacle.

Conclusions.

Consideration of issues related to politics and statehood processes in a symbolic way is promising from a philosophical point of view. Interesting, in our opinion, is the interpretation of philosophical and anthropological symbolism, the study of the connections between politics, on the one hand, and corporeality and sexuality, on the other. A separate field of philosophical and anthropological research on this issue is the symbolization of politics as sexual perversion. This analysis allows us to trace how the attack of power on a person - in particular, on his bodily autonomy - occurs.

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